

INFLUENCE OF IMPREGNATION DIE SETUP ON THE PROPERTIES OF UNIDIRECTIONAL THERMOPLASTIC TAPES

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1 Abstract

Composite materials find widespread use nowadays, often in applications where the superior balance of mechanical properties and low density is an advantage over other materials. Such composites often consist of glass or carbon fibres and thermosetting matrices, like epoxy or polyurethane, which results in high mechanical properties and good thermal stability. However, these composites also exhibit some drawbacks, like issues in recycling and reuse due to the thermosetting matrix. Another point is, that the composites cannot be remolten after curing, which prohibits thermoforming and using overmoulding as an approach to connect the composite to other structural components. Thus, considerable interest in using thermoplastic matrices in such composites exists, especially when thinking of applications where high numbers of parts are needed, as in automotive applications.

During the production of unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic tapes in an extrusion-based melt-impregnation, beside the melt viscosity and the process velocity, the impregnation die setup has a significant influence on the morphology of thermoplastic UD-tapes. Various literature and patent researches describe a corrugated channel within the impregnation nozzle as a critical feature of efficient fiber impregnation.

A flow simulation, using ANSYS Fluent helped to find suitable wave parameters. For this purpose, two variants of a wavy channel are compared to the existing straight channel geometry (see Fig.1).

The simulation showed an improved impregnation by a higher deflection of the fibers and an increased pressurization. The wave-shaped channel with the best simulation result was manufactured as an insert and integrated into the existing impregnation nozzle.

The aim of this work was to investigate the effect of a wavy channel of an extrusion die on the impregnation quality by determining morphological parameters. In terms of the fiber volume content, a satisfying result has been achieved compared to a commercially available UD-tape. However, the porosity calculated from the theoretically possible density and the actually measured density of the tapes produced is below those purchased (see Fig.2, 3). To examine the homogeneity of the fibre distribution, microscopic cross-sectional images of the UD-tapes were extracted perpendicular to the fibre direction. The following optical analysis by light microscope and scanning electron microscope show a positive influence of the newly developed nozzle geometry on the fibre distribution (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 2 Fibre volume content of various materials

Fig. 3 Porosity various materials

Fig. 4 Impregnation of carbon fibres

